

Review on SUAV targets positioning and tracking with RTK GPS systems for LOS maintenance

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Abstract: The use of Small Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (SUAV's) is rapidly increasing in civilian and military applications, but their cost, accessibility and easy usage make them potential tools for malicious activities. This review presents a comprehensive analysis of current SUAV detection and classification techniques. The SUAV detection methods include Radar Based Sensing, RF signal analysis, Acoustic signatures and Vision based systems. Findings show that single-sensor methods are insufficient, while hybrid approaches combining micro-Doppler, RF, and acoustic signatures offer higher detection accuracy. For precise SUAV navigation, this review discusses RTK GPS technology which uses carrier phase measurements and Integer ambiguity resolution by LAMBDA method for sub-centimetre accuracy. This paper also discusses IMU sensor integration with GPS sensor to provide high accuracy and real time positioning and navigation. The study also analyses Line of Sight (LOS) alignment strategies for air-to-ground and air-to-air communication, comparing gimbal-based alignment with monopulse tracking and FSOC based approaches. While gimbal mechanisms are reliable but slow, monopulse and EKF-based methods provide faster and more precise alignment. Overall, effective SUAV surveillance requires multi-sensor integration, advanced signal processing, and robust communication links. Future improvements in AI-driven fusion, swarm-based detection, GNSS alternatives, and autonomous FSO alignment can significantly enhance system reliability and performance.

Keywords: SUAV, Micro-Doppler, RTK GPS, NMEA, RTCM, LoRa, NTRIP.

I. INTRODUCTION

Small Unmanned Aerial Vehicles have rapidly become popular technology across civilian and defence sector. Because of their light weight structure, ease of deployment, affordability and accessibility they are suitable for a wide range of applications such as precision farming, traffic and environmental monitoring, disaster response, surveillance etc. However, with great power comes great responsibility, but these advantages can be exploited for malicious purposes like illegal surveillance, smuggling operations, weaponised drone attacks etc. Thus, this paper highlights the urgent need for effective SUAV detection and classification techniques. Fig. 1 highlights the illegal activities that can be done by SUAV's [1].

Accurate Navigation and Positioning is an important aspect in Military and Civil applications of SUAV's. Standard GPS services provide meter level accuracy which becomes insufficient in critical tasks. Hence there is a need of a precise system which can provide sub-centimetre accuracy. To address this limitation RTK (Real Time Kinematic) GPS is used, it provides us high precision positioning using carrier phase measurements and real time corrections from fixed base station. To achieve reliable and smooth navigation RTK is paired with IMU and Kalman Filter.

Fig. 1 Illegal use of SUAV

Additionally, this paper also discusses stable communication links for FSOC (Free Space Optical Communication). FSOC offers high speed and interference free data transfer, but it demands highly accurate LOS alignment. Various techniques for Air to Air and Air to Ground, LOS alignment techniques are discussed.

This report provides a comprehensive review of current strategies and technologies for SUAV detection and classification, high precision positioning and navigation using RTK GPS and LOS alignment techniques in SUAV systems. The aim is to clearly explain how different types of sensors, smart filtering algorithms, and strong communication systems work together to build SUAV monitoring solutions that are accurate, secure, and dependable for both civilian and defence use.

A. Key Literature Addressing Radar and FSO:

Recent literature reflects a wide and diverse set of advancements across radar sensing [129, 131], signal processing, and free-space optical communication. Work on photonic radar architectures has explored improved opto-electronic oscillator designs [102], while subsurface-scanning systems have benefited from SFCW-based GPR developments [103, 114] and enhanced clutter-suppression techniques for foliage-penetrating radar imaging [104]. Research efforts have also introduced digital architectures for real-time time-frequency imaging [105] and comprehensive reviews capturing the evolution of modern remote-sensing radar technologies [106, 116]. In the signal-processing domain, contributions include improved micro-Doppler classification through tuned R-PCA+SVM models [107], simplified receiver designs for OTFS-based SAR [108], interference-resilient OTFS waveform configurations [119], and empirical-wavelet-based approaches for posture and cadence-frequency imaging [109]. Additional progress has been demonstrated through X-band and C-band FMCW radar designs [110, 115, 128, 135], feature extraction methods for intrapulse LPI waveforms [111], CW-radar data-acquisition systems [112, 127], and UWB-based human-presence detection solutions [113].

Parallel developments in optical wireless communication highlight intelligent beam-steering approaches using fuzzy-logic controllers [117], OFDM-based radar system implementations [118], and detailed reviews on FSO-link security and modern fibreless-communication trends [120]. Surveys on acquisition, tracking, and pointing (ATP) mechanisms and beam-profile correction techniques further emphasize system-level challenges in FSO links [123, 130].

Foundational research also addresses atmospheric turbulence, proposing neural-based beam-wander mitigation [124, 125], turbulence-induced fading compensation [126], season-wise attenuation modeling [132], and weather-driven optical-attenuation formulations [133]. Complementary optical studies include adaptive beam-steering for terrestrial links [134], PID-based stabilization techniques [136], and AI-enabled approaches for improving FSO reliability [137].

Additional radar-focused contributions include detection algorithms for fast-moving FMCW targets [138], introductory frameworks for FSO communication fundamentals [139], foliage-target detection methodologies [121], and UAV-classification strategies using micro-Doppler signatures [122]. Altogether, these works collectively map the ongoing advancements shaping next-generation radar and optical-communication systems.

II. SUAV TARGET DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES

Small Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (SUAVs) are emerging as one of the most influential technologies in today's rapidly evolving world. Their presence can be seen across a wide range of sectors, where they are revolutionizing operations and decision-making processes [1,15]. SUAVs play a vital role in both military and civilian applications, owing to the remarkable advantages they offer. Their compact size allows them to operate in confined or hard-to-reach areas, while their high durability ensures reliable performance even in challenging environmental conditions [26,30]. Because of these advantages, SUAV's are widely used for Traffic Monitoring, Agricultural Management, Forest Fire Detection, Civil Infrastructure monitoring, Disaster management, Marine environmental management and military applications [57-64].

There are various types of SUAV targets, some of the most commonly used classes of SUAV's are: - two-blade rotor, a three-short-blade rotor, a three-long-blade rotor, a quadcopter, a bionic bird and a two-blade-rotor [5]. Figure 2 shows various SUAV targets [4]

Fig. 2 Representation of SUAV targets

Due to all these benefits, they can be used for illicit purposes such as Drone Attacks (SUAV's carrying explosive and biological/chemical weapons), Illegal smuggling (Illegal Drugs, chemicals and weapons), Drone espionage (Privacy breaching), Drone collisions (Intentionally disturbing aerial appliances) [1]. That is why there is a rising demand in detection and classification techniques of SUAV's. There are multiple ways for the detection of the SUAV's, most commonly used techniques are:

A. Radar Based Detection

Radar is considered one of the most trust worthy technology used for detecting aerial vehicles as it measures their distance, direction, speed and size [13, 83, 87, 97]. It is used in military as well as civilian applications. Radar emits electromagnetic waves which gets reflected from surrounding objects. High frequency radars detect micro-doppler [17] signatures caused by small, fast and periodic motions of the small parts of the target SUAV. Examples include rotating of drone blades and flapping of wings of a bird [14].

These micro-doppler signatures [81,82,101] are different for varying SUAV's and multiple datasets are present for classification based on these specific signatures. *DIAT- μ SAT* is a free access dataset consisting of 4849 micro-doppler spectrogram images of 5 SUAV's. It can be used to train various AI models to classify the SUAV's based on their specific micro-doppler signatures. When the data was collected, parameters of the SUAV targets such as rotor RPM and flapping frequency of wing was varied for higher number of data points [4]. One of the major drawbacks of Radar based detection is that birds and wildlife interfere in the echoes of SUAV's. This can lead to false alarms and operational inefficiency.

B. RF based Detection

RF based Detection is one of the most efficient ways of SUAV detection. As there are various RF based electronics components on the SUAV's like GPS receivers, radio link between controller and SUAV, live video transfer etc. Majority of the SUAV's operate within the 2.4 GHz ISM (Industrial, Scientific and Medical) frequency band. RF scanners passively detect the signals used by SUAV's and determines its location based on the strength of the detected signal [65]. Figure 3 shows a RF based detection system [1].

Fig. 3 RF based Detection System

In RF based SUAV detection the communication frequency spectrum is monitored and analysed. Some of the detection techniques are monitoring the frequency of data packet transmission at 2.4 GHz. If drone communication is via WiFi or other Access Point (AP) then the detection is done by monitoring the data packet length [66].

In this system there is a chance of frequency overlapping and signal jamming which causes interference which leads to the inability of our system to detect RF signals from SUAV's.

C. Acoustic based Detection

During the operation of SUAV's acoustic noise is generated by its rotor blades and motor. This noise can be detected by an array of microphones, which allows us to locate the aerial targets. Different SUAV's have their distinct acoustic noise signatures that allows us to classify them. These different signatures vary in frequency, amplitude etc [1].

There is pre-existing work on the acoustic based drone surveillance system by [68] in which the entire system consists of a spherical microphone array composed of 120 elements and a video camera. The issue with this setup is the distance to the object has to be known or calibrated manually due to its limited depth of acoustic focusing.

In [67] Zhiguo Shi *et al.* proposed a system which gives high accuracy and 24/7 availability. It uses an effective feature extraction method on which SVM is applied, to eliminate multiple paths in drone localization process they used TDOA (Time Delay of Arrival) algorithm.

In this system ambient noise, background noise and wind can create unwanted noises which can mask the acoustic signatures of target SUAV making it difficult to detect.

D. Vision based Detection

Vision based Detection uses cameras (IR, thermal, multi spectral) [8,10,27] and deep learning algorithms to detect and classify the SUAV's. It works on Optical Signature Detection like shape of the object, motion and appearance. This system is mainly used for identifying aerial objects with low RCS (Radar Cross Section) [69-70].

Fig. 4 Vision based Detection.

This detection technique has some limitations that leads to poor accuracy like low lighting, bad weather conditions, obstruction etc [71].

E. Sensor Fusion for detection

Detecting SUAV's is quite challenging as they are small, fast and often made with composite materials making them hard to detect using a single sensor. Hence there is a requirement to build a robust and fault proof detection system using sensor fusion [12]. Detection of SUAV's can be improved by collecting and combining data from multiple sensors. It used probabilistic data to increase detection of the SUAV's.

There are three types of fusion levels: -

- 1) Data level: - It includes integrating raw sensor signals like RADAR + LIDAR point clouds
- 2) Feature Level: - It includes integrating raw data which has been extracted by multiple sensors without any analysis or processing.
- 3) Decision level: - It processes the data that includes decisions or confidence scores from multiple sensors [1].

Overall, multi-modal sensing significantly enhances situational awareness by combining complementary sensor strengths, providing more reliable detection and tracking than any single sensor alone.

F. Classification of detected SUAV's

Ensuring protection against SUAV's is important for the national security. Thus, there is a need for advanced surveillance systems capable of automatically detecting and classifying low RCS aerial targets [5]. Radar Based Detection is the most popular method for detection of SUAV targets. Because it comes with various advantage such as operating in day/night, any weather condition, foliage environment, wide area coverage etc [4,6]. Deep Learning (DL) supported m-D (Micro Doppler) [33] and Machine Learning Algorithm are two primary classification techniques for low RCS aerial targets. But Machine Learning Algorithm requires manual feature extraction, which is difficult because it requires accurate listing, extracting multiple essential features, hence DL supported m-D based SUAV target classification is preferred [2,4,11].

III. RTK GPS FOR POSITIONING

Global Positioning System (GPS) is a satellite-based navigation system that provides us the coordinates and time information everywhere. GPS receiver can determine its position with the help of multiple satellites (GPS, GLONASS, Galileo, NavIC, BeiDou etc) [53] with an accuracy within a few meters, which is sufficient for general navigation but not enough for applications such as autonomous vehicles, land surveying, drone guidance etc. To overcome such limitations, Differential GPS (DGPS) is used, which improves accuracy by using a fixed base station that transmits correction data to nearby receiver. DGPS typically achieves 2–3-meter accuracy by compensating for satellite and ionospheric errors. However, this level of accuracy is not adequate for military applications. Thus, RTK (Real Time Kinematic)-GPS technology is employed which gives us sub-centimetre level accuracy [47,50,51].

A. Trilateration

Trilateration is a method which is used to determine the exact co-ordinates of any point on earth by measuring the distances from minimum 4 reference points and is thus useful in GNSS system.

Fig. 5 Trilateration Methodology

If we generate an imaginary sphere around the satellite with radius equal to the distance between the satellite and the receiver, the intersection of these 4 spheres determines the precise location of the receiver. The GPS receiver quartz clocks are synchronized with atomic clock present in each satellite. Satellite sends an RF signal, which contains information about its origin time from the satellite. Then the receiver collects this signal and calculates its distance from the satellite by measuring the time difference between transmission and reception of the signal. DGPS is an enhanced version of GPS which uses a base station and a receiver to eliminate satellite and atmospheric errors. The base station is setup at a known location and it transmits correction data to the receiver via a Network or Radio link. This increases the accuracy of the GPS receiver.

Fig. 6 DGPS Methodology

This enhancement in precision of location by DGPS makes it useful for applications like, marine navigation, land surveying, autonomous vehicle guidance systems etc. To overcome the drawbacks of Differential GPS, RTK-GPS technology is employed in military applications.

B. RTK (Real Time Kinematic)-GPS

In RTK-GPS Sinusoidal Carrier Waves play a crucial role in achieving centimetre level accuracy. The signal received by the RTK-GPS receiver is a Pseudo-Random Code modulated on a sinusoidal carrier wave, this code consists of information of approximate position with meter level accuracy. The high frequency sinusoidal carrier allows much finer distance measurement between satellite and the rover. The carrier wave frequency (1575.42 MHz, $\lambda= 19\text{cm}$) belongs to L-band frequency spectrum. RTK-GPS calculates its accurate distance with the given formula:

$$D = \lambda(N + \phi)$$

Where, D is the Distance between satellite and receiver, N is the total number of sinusoidal cycles, Φ is the fractional sine wave and λ is the wavelength of the sine wave. RTK-GPS receiver compares the phase (ϕ) of sinusoidal carrier wave received from the satellite with a wave of same frequency generated by its local oscillator (LO) [25]. This allows it to determine the fraction of the wavelength of the carrier wave [52]. Here, the total number of sinusoidal cycles are unknown and this creates Integer Ambiguity error which can be solved by using LAMBDA method. It is a mathematical model which applies integer transformation operations to the ambiguity vectors, thus reducing the correlations between different measurements. LAMBDA method uses different measurements from DGPS system to create multiple datasets which increases the accuracy of number of sinusoidal cycles [7,48].

Fig. 7 Sinusoidal Carrier Phase Wave

Once the integer ambiguity is resolved, the system transitions from Float (Temporary Fix) to Fixed RTK solution providing us with sub-centimetre level accuracy. This makes RTK-GPS useful in certain applications requiring high precision such as, drone trajectory mapping, autonomous vehicle positioning and land surveying.

NMEA (National Marine Electronics Association) and RTCM (Radio Technical Commission for Maritime services) are two main data communication standards used in GNSS systems. NMEA is a standard format for transmitting GPS data in the form of ASCII text sentences like "\$GPGGA", "\$GPRMC", "\$GPGSV" which contains information like, Latitude, Longitude, Altitude, Time and Satellite Status. These messages are widely used in GPS receivers and external devices (Microcontrollers) for communication, which allows these systems to read real time data in a simple and human readable form. Whereas RTCM is a binary communication protocol specifically designed for transmitting correction data which used in high accuracy application systems such as RTK-GPS. RTCM messages are sent from the base station to the rover, which eliminates the satellite and atmospheric errors thereby increasing rover accuracy.

RTK-GPS has multiple civil as well as military applications such as, Land Surveying, Bridge mapping, Town planning, Robust Navigation for UAV's, monitoring challenging environmental conditions, high yield agricultural practises, Measuring Vehicle Attitude and various Military applications [9, 34-46, 49].

In summary, RTK-enabled GNSS provides centimetre-level accuracy critical for SUAV navigation, though it must be supported by fallback systems to handle signal degradation or outages

C. Communication between Base Station and the Receiver

To transmit the correction data from the base station to the rover module we require a wireless communication link between them. Some of the most frequently used communication methods for RTK GPS are LORA and NTRIP [20, 21, 23, 24].

LoRa (Long Range): - LoRa is a low power, long range wireless communication technology. In RTK GPS system it is used to transmit the RTCM correction data form base station to the receiver without internet. It is majorly used in areas with less or no network availability.

NTRIP (Network Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol): - It is the standard protocol used to transmit RTCM from Base station to the receiver via internet. NTRIP protocol has three layers which includes Client(rover), Server (base station) and the Caster (broker/gateway).

IV. DEAD RECKONING USING IMU INTEGRATION

Dead Reckoning is a navigation method that helps us in situations where GPS signal becomes weak. In such scenarios we don't get satellite data and thus the system estimates the current position with the help of previous position, speed, motion and direction data collected from the IMU. The GNSS receiver gives current positional coordinates but when the signal is weak or lost it relies on IMU sensors [56] which consists of accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer, these sensors keep tracking motion and continues updating position. This allows smooth navigation without interruption.

The Kalman Filter is an algorithm which is used in RTK GPS for combining data from GNSS sensor and IMU [75-77], providing more accurate positioning [18, 19]. This entire system prevents position loss, maintains smooth trajectory and hence makes RTK system robust in real time applications [78, 79].

KALMAN Filter Working

In [75-77] we can see the application of integration of the extended Kalman filter, IMU sensor and the GPS sensor. The IMU has higher frequency data update than the GPS sensor but it does not have positional accuracy and is prone to drift. GPS sensor has higher positional accuracy than the IMU sensor, but low data updating rate.

We get advantages of both these methods collectively by implementing a Kalman Filter that estimates accurate position by estimating true value from noisy measurements.

To understand it more clearly let's consider an example of a drone using integrated GPS+IMU sensors for navigation. In the first step, i.e. The Prediction Step the GPS provides the drones current position and the IMU sensor provides the estimated position for the next time interval (1 sec). In the second step, i.e. The Update Step we get the accurate position from GPS (Higher accuracy can be obtained from RTK GPS) after a certain time interval (1 sec). Hence, we now have 2 estimated positions of our drone's current location. In the third step, i.e. Kalman Gain, the algorithm estimates uncertainty of both the sensors, then it calculates Kalman gain for each sensor which tells us which sensor to trust more. Finally, we obtain a high precise position by fusion of GPS and IMU sensor data with Kalman Filter.

V. TECHNIQUES FOR LOS ALIGNMENT

Reliable Line of Sight alignment is an important aspect in Free Space Optical Communication (FSOC) [80,85,86,88,89]. As the transmitter and the receiver move continuously on ground, in air and space, the pointing accuracy and the tracking bandwidth needs to be stabilized [91,92,96,98]. This stabilization and alignment is important to ensure high data transfer rate, reducing Bit Error Rate (BER) and preventing link failure.

Major advantages of FSO over RF communication are high data transfer rate, security and resistance to interference [71, 90, 94]. FSOC is used for high-speed, long-distance wireless data links in areas where laying fiber is difficult, such as remote or disaster-hit regions. It is widely used in satellite communication, inter-UAV links, last-mile connectivity, and secure military communication due to its high bandwidth and low interference. [100]

Techniques for LOS alignment between

a) Air to Ground

AG FSOC links are widely used transfer data (images/videos) from SUAV's to ground with capabilities such as more security and high data rate[93]. Because the SUAV's are moving continuously, maintaining an accurate LOS link requires robust pointing and tracking mechanism. Common AG LOS alignment techniques are: -

Gimbal based tracking physically steers its optical beam using servo motors in these cases [16, 28, 54, 94, 99]. Radar based detection is often used for locating SUAV's initially and hence pointing and directing the beam towards the SUAV. To improve the tracking accuracy the concept called multiple sensor fusion is integrated which includes: -

- GPS coordinates of SUAV [22, 31]
- IMU measurements
- Extended Kalman Filter (EKF)

This combination of sensors enhances system stability especially in long ranges of operations.

Monopulse based tracking technique estimates angular deviation by continuously measuring it from closely spaced array of antennas. This system forms sum and difference channels enabling real time calculation of target detection. It is highly resistant to noise and suitable in operations where signal fluctuation is a major issue [72, 73, 84].

b) Air to Air

Establishing FSOC link in AA system is complex because of the target noise and the receiver's own motion [3, 29]. To establish good communication link, we need to consider relative position, relative velocity and target acceleration [55]. To establish and maintain LOS, AA systems require precise estimation of relative position, velocity and orientation.

Relative Position estimation

In this GPS is used for determining each SUAV's position, but if higher accuracy is required, especially during tight beam alignment, RTK GPS is used to minimize positional error to centimeter level.

Relative Velocity and Attitude estimation

IMU (Gyroscopes and accelerometers) provides accurate measurements for predicting motion dynamics. Fusing IMU with GPS improves robustness during GPS dropouts.

EKF based state estimation

Vinod K *et al.* [74] used 9 states extended Kalman filter (EKF) to estimate the state vector using the noisy radar measurements and own-ship inertial navigation system (INS). The EKF offered improved tracking accuracy and dynamic response, for getting stable AA FSOC, even under harsh conditions.

Existing AA and AG LOS alignment techniques still face major challenges such as different atmospheric conditions, temporary loss of GPS signal and vibration induced jitter. These issues make it difficult for dynamic operations in unpredictable environment. Future work should explore machine learning based prediction models that will help us to detect motion before it happens.

VI. CONCLUSION

Small unmanned aerial vehicles (SUAV's) are becoming popular for civilian and military applications, due to their low cost, ease of operation and high availability they can be used for malicious activities. Hence there is a need of surveillance systems that detect and classify SUAV's. This review presents a detailed analysis of multiple SUAV detection techniques such as Radar based detection, RF based signal analysis, acoustic sensing, vision-based systems and sensor fusion methods. This survey concludes that using a single sensor for SUAV detection is insufficient and hence hybrid systems which combines m-D (Micro Doppler), acoustic and RF spectral signatures provides more accuracy in aerial target detection.

Accuracy in navigation and positioning of SUAV's is important for robust surveillance systems. This review emphasizes on methodology of RTK GPS technology. It shows the role of carrier-phase measurements, integer ambiguity resolution, and the LAMBDA method in RTK GPS for achieving centimetre level accuracy. Since GPS systems are susceptible to outages and signal losses, IMU based dead reckoning and Kalman filter fusion were discussed for reliable for accurate SUAV positioning.

The paper also analysed Line of Sight (LOS) alignment strategies for air-to-ground and air-to-air communication. It discusses the advantages of FSOC over RF communication and methods of aligning such LOS in AA and AG systems. AG systems use Gimbal based alignment using data from GPS and IMU sensors placed on UAV whereas Mono-pulse method uses an array of antennas that detect reflected waves from target to accurately estimate range, azimuth and elevation angles. Although gimbal-based methods are mature and widely used, their mechanical nature limits response speed for highly dynamic UAV trajectories. In contrast, mono-pulse tracking and EKF-based fusion offer faster and more precise LOS estimation, but require high-quality sensors and powerful onboard computation.

Overall, this review highlights that effective SUAV detection and navigation require multi-sensor integration, advanced signal processing, and robust communication architectures. Future research should explore AI-driven sensor fusion models, swarm-based cooperative detection, resilient GNSS alternatives, and autonomous alignment systems for long-range FSO links. With these advancements, next-generation SUAV detection systems can achieve higher accuracy, reliability, and operational resilience across both civilian and defence scenarios.

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